

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13963069

Administrative Strategies For Effective Use Of Social Media Packages In Public Secondary School In Abakaliki Zone

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of Secondary School Principals' use of social media on their administrative strategies in Ebonyi State. Five specific objectives with three related research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was used in the study. 452 principals of public secondary schools in Ebonyi State made up the study's population. There was no sampling because the population served as the sample. The researcher created the "Social Media Usage on Administrative Strategies of Secondary School Principals Questionnaire" (SMUASSSQ), a 40-item structured questionnaire with a reliability coefficient of 0.73 that was utilized as a data gathering tool. To address the research issues, the obtained data were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation, and the t-test of independence statistics was employed to assess the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings showed that Ebonyi State's public secondary school principals may use social media to improve staff relations, handle conflicts within the staff, foster community-school collaboration, foster staff teamwork, and guarantee fair distribution of instructional resources. Furthermore, no discernible variation was observed in the average evaluations of urban and rural principals concerning their utilization of social media for improving staff-to-staff communication, handling staff conflicts, improving school-community collaboration, fostering teamwork among staff, and guaranteeing fair distribution of educational materials. Among other things, principals should use social media to quickly communicate with personnel and make sure that balance is achieved in order to improve contact with stakeholders, according to the study's conclusions.

Keywords: Administrative Strategies for effective use of social media packages in public secondary school.

INTRODUCTION

The importance of social media in today's world cannot be overstated. Social media has become an increasingly important part of peoples' daily lives and has experienced tremendous growth Alabi, (2017) Because educational institutions and students are increasingly using social media platforms for communication and engagement, the effects of this phenomena are especially noticeable in the field of education Chen, & Wang, (2021) Joo, (2020) assert that the dynamic digital era presents considerable prospects for the use of social media in educational communication management. Therefore, this medium has the ability to improve knowledge exchange, increase accessibility to information, and promote collaboration between staff, students, and administrators, Ogunbiyi (2017) noted that Social Media platforms have the potential to serve as a valuable instrument for fostering community engagement and enhancing involvement in educational endeavors.

Digital platforms that enable online communication, content sharing, and user involvement are referred to as social media. Alabi, (2017) claim that these platforms let users create personal pages or profiles, send messages, share photos, videos, and other kinds of content, as well as take part in a

variety of social activities. Among the popular social media sites are YouTube, WhatsApp, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter. The actual meaning of the phrase "social media" is not well defined. This study will, nevertheless, continue the body of research that has shown that scholars have regularly concentrated on particular platforms or apps, albeit in various contexts. Take "Facebook" (Lim, 2012) and "Twitter" (Delery and Roumpi, 2017). It is clear from all of the aforementioned definitions that the authors all seem to have agreed that using internet technologies for interactions is a necessary part of social media. Therefore, for the purposes of this paper, "social media" refers to any internet-based platform or application that has been created to promote communication and interaction, including networking. Examples of such applications include podcasting, content tagging services, wikis (Wikipedia), blogs and microblogs on Twitter, social networking sites like Facebook and LinkedIn, multimedia sharing services like YouTube and Netflix, and content syndication like RSS feeds.

The availability and utilization of social media platforms and applications have increased significantly as a result of the incredible technical advancements of the 21st century. Social media appears to have fundamentally changed and reshaped how people interact and communicate, making it a valuable source of revolutionary information. Without a doubt, social media is essential for the spread of information, whether it be political, spectacular, sensitive, or just everyday knowledge. The main goal of social media platforms is to facilitate social interactions and information exchange among users; however they differ in terms of features and functioning. The introduction of social media platforms has brought about a substantial change in the ways in which people communicate, interact, and share information (Shahbaznezhad, Dolan and Rashidirad, 2021). As noted by Chen and Wang (2021), Social media platforms have emerged as a significant medium for disseminating news, advocating for ideas, endorsing products or services, and establishing both social and professional connections. It is imperative here to note that sharing idea. In the context of this study Social Media is an administrative tools or strategies adopted by the principals of secondary schools for sharing of information, idea, knowledge and skills to the students or staff.

The administration of secondary schools is concerned with running the institution as a whole. Ogunbiyi (2017) defines school administration as the process of utilizing the material and human resources that are available in schools to accomplish tasks in order to meet pre-established goals. The author went on to say that as school administration is goal-oriented; it is concerned with the efficient and cost-effective management of resources. This is done to optimize benefits and reduce drawbacks for the system that is being managed. Principals in charge of schools collaborate with faculty, students, and the community to accomplish objectives. To accomplish predetermined goals, it entails the employment of personnel, resources, and money (Ugwuanyi, 2013). The achievement of organizational goals and objectives, in the opinion of Alabi (2017), is the most important component of the school as an organization. Therefore, the objectives of secondary school education as outlined in the National Policy on Education will not be met in the absence of proper and attentive management, the utilization of quality resources, and group interaction. According to Alabi (2017), administration includes the following: coordinating people's efforts to achieve their stated goals; implementing the policies of the Board of Education; and leading and managing activities carried out by those holding formal positions of responsibility and authority within an organization.

Based on the aforementioned, it can be concluded that administration is an intentional endeavor that involves organizing the combination of material and human resources in order to accomplish specific organizational goals and objectives. Planning, organizing, directing, and supervising people's efforts toward the accomplishment of goals is the primary goal of administration in every organization (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN, 2014). Within the framework of this investigation, secondary school administration is defined as the process of uniting faculty, students, and the community using social media platforms to accomplish the declared educational aims and objectives. Therefore, it is impossible for secondary school administration in the modern day to function without utilizing contemporary technology media.

The use of Social Media by the principals in school administration can foster and encourage teamwork among staff, which raises morale, lessens production hiccups, and enhances service quality (Afriveni and Masbiran, 2021; Ahmed, 2019; Jalali and Heidari, 2016) and in fostering good relationship between the school and the host community. Collaboration between schools and the

community is a key component of principals' public relations efforts to ensure that the public is aware of their operations and instructional requirements (Sanfo, 2020). In order to achieve educational objectives, schools work in partnership with the community, particularly parents (Ginosyan, Tuzlukova and Ahmed, 2020). Therefore, the realization of the shared accountability between the school and the community by the principal in the execution of his/her administrative strategies is reflected in the school's public relations efforts. This is pivotal because the community or parents' support can help schools provide high-quality instruction (Sanfo, 2020). This shows that schools must build strong public relations strategies. It is also anticipated therefore, that the deployment of principals' e-leadership will improve the efficiency of schools public relations, but this has not yet been shown.

Furthermore, through digital interaction that social media offers, principals can connect to share views regarding instructional processes in the school. This will give students who find it difficult to express themselves in public to confidently air their opinion regarding activities in the school especially as it concerns their academic and social wellbeing (Ahmed, 2019). Furthermore, use of Social Media discussion forums allows students to share information with their peers, learn from them as well and this has been found to improve their learning (Joo, 2020; Oishi, 2020). However, other than that, the difficulties in assessment are what make the switch from face-to-face to mobile learning the most difficult. Rahmadi (2020) added that even if staff and students use Social Media frequently in real life, things are different in a learning circle; stressing that they are passive and ill-equipped to learn using Social media actively, collaboratively, and independently. Equally, high-performing staff and students are among those who participate in social media discussions, as opposed to low-performers who are typically quiet (Niah, 2021). Thus, Egenti and Ebenebe (2018) posited that school administrators must ensure that Social Media is allowed for use by only staff and senior students especially those in penultimate/or in examination class. However, the extent principals use Social Media applications or packages may vary depending on gender and location.

The physical characteristics of a school that set it apart from others in terms of structures, materials, access roads, pipes, water, electricity, and people are referred to as its location. According to Okorie and Ezech (2016), a school's location is a specific spot within its physical environment—whether it be rural or urban—in relation to other locations. Although humans have an endless capacity for learning, their ability to do so may be constrained by the facilities and behavioral norms of the immediate school setting (Oredein, 2016). Idialu (2013) defines rural areas as those areas that are distinct from towns and cities with little to no basic amenities or facilities, whereas urban areas are those densely populated towns or cities with the basic amenities (electricity, good roads, good health facilities and internet facilities, etc.) that make life comfortable. It is noteworthy that as urbanization progresses, educational chances for members of the urban-rural social mix are likewise undergoing fundamental changes. These changes include improvements in both number and scale of educational opportunities. The divide between urban and rural communities extends beyond the economic sphere and contributes to the unequal distribution of educational resources between them.

For example, principals may find it difficult to use social media applications effectively and efficiently in rural schools due to poor network coverage, low installation of electric gadgets, and inadequate electricity supplies. In contrast, good network coverage, relatively adequate electricity supplies, and installed network gadgets in urban areas facilitate the use of social media in schools. The notion put forth by Yu-you and Zhi-hui (2017) that the "urban priority" policy contributes to significant educational disparities under the urban-rural separation school system supported this scenario. On the one hand, Jun and Chudan (2017) note that the narrowing of the gap between urban and rural investment in education can hardly conceal the actual gap in the level and quality of basic education between urban and rural areas.

The ways that Ebonyi State's rural and urban secondary schools differ from one another may be reflected in how social media packages are used in secondary school administration. For example, Rahmadi (2020) and Zhang et al. (2022) claimed that communities with consistent energy supplies and internet access tend to utilize social media more frequently. Joo (2020), however, found that the decision to use social media in school management is not largely influenced by one's location. More research in this area is required due to the inconsistent findings in the literature about the impact of location on social media use in school administration. However, considering the immense benefits

that Social Media as a social media has been espoused to bring to the development of education but with little or no evidence-based research on the impacts it exerts on principals' administrative effectiveness, it becomes imperative to investigate the Social Media usage in the administration of secondary school principals of Ebonyi State.

Statement of problem

Perhaps the world has gone into a global village, in the village everything is cooperated into a single unit of association, education and entertainment through advance technology. In the world everybody can have their meeting, relate with one another through a part way call social media. In school administration, principals work load can be schedule online which is faster in reaching out to stakeholders if the needs arise. It also promotes cordial relationship between teachers and students. Social media application has offered effective communication with staff personnel in resolving problems that could have be a detrimental impact on all parties involved and the school. Social media application has aided principals in Ebonyi state in resolving issues affecting staff personnel. More so principals use social media application to pass information as quick as possible unlike letter writing or other forms of communication in time past. Furthermore, social media application may have helped principals to resolve conflict among staff. Principals uses social media platform to find out facts about conflict and resolve it among staff without physical appearance.

In other hand students use social media to inform principal of the roles or behavioural attitude of different teachers without the teacher knowing the source of the information and the behaviour of the teacher can be modifying through social media platform. Social media application may also have contributed to helping the principal in effective decision making as roles of different units can be share before the resumption of school and certain decision of the school can be resolved through social media application. However, irrespective of the benefits social media platform can offer in education and in school administration in particular most principals seem not to use it in school administration. Suddenly the researcher visits to some schools' interaction with some principals proved that they don't have the skill and the knowledge in handing android phone making it impossible to copy in school administration in this era of internet world. Therefore, the thrust of the study was to determine extent social media usage on administration of secondary school principals of Ebonyi state.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to ascertain the influence of social media usage on administration of secondary school principals of Ebonyi state. Specifically, the study determined the;

1. extent principals' use social media to enhance school-community collaboration among staff in secondary school in Ebonyi state
2. extent principals' use social media to encourage teamwork among staff secondary school in Ebonyi state
3. extent pricipals' use social media to share instructional resources in the school.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. To what extent do principals' use social media to enhance school-community collaboration in secondary school administration in Ebonyi state
2. To what extent do principals' use social media to encourage teamwork among staff secondary school administration in Ebonyi state
3. To what extent do principals use social media to share instructional resources in secondary school administration in Ebonyi state.

Hypotheses

The following three (3) null hypotheses guided the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

HO1 There is no significant difference between the mean rating of rural and urban school principals on the extent principals' use social media to enhance school-community collaboration in secondary schools in Ebonyi state

Ho2; There is no significant difference between the mean rating of rural and urban school principals on the extent principals' use social media to encourage teamwork among staff in secondary schools in Ebonyi state

HO3; There I no significant difference between the mean rating of rural and urban school principals on the extent principals’ use social media to share instructional resources in secondary schools in Ebonyi state.

METHODOLOGY

For this investigation, a descriptive survey design type was chosen. A descriptive study can gather data from a broad population by using instruments such as checklists, interviews, questionnaires, and observational schedules, among others. This design was chosen because it allowed the researcher to utilize descriptive statistics and a questionnaire to gain in-depth knowledge about the use of social media by Ebonyi State secondary school principals without modifying the independent variable. Four hundred and fifty-two (452) junior and senior principals from 226 public secondary schools in Ebonyi State made up the study's population (Source: SEB, 2023). Since the population is manageable, all 452 principals were used for the study, making census sampling the method of choice. The instrument for data collection was a 40 items structured questionnaire on Principals Use of Social Media in the administration of public secondary schools in Ebonyi State. Data collected was analyzed descriptively using mean and standard deviation statistics to answer the research questions and t-test of independence to test the hypotheses.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent do principals’ use Social Media to enhance school-community collaboration in secondary school administration in Ebonyi State?*

In table1 below, data gotten from respondents were analysed to show the extent principals use social media to enhance school-community collaboration in secondary school administration in Ebonyi State.

Table 1: Mean responses of the respondents on the extent principals’ use Social Media to enhance community collaboration in secondary school administration in Ebonyi State

S/N	Items: Social Media	N	Mean	S.D.	Decision
1	aids the principal to spend time in order to properly compose text messages so as to get the best inputs from stakeholders	396	3.62	0.49	Always
2	affords the principal opportunity to engage with other principals on administrative discourse which enriches their decision making in vital school matters	396	3.64	0.48	Always
3	helps to communicate issues of the school easily to staff/parents even when it involves a complex decision	396	3.23	0.44	Often
4	help principals to manage the staff activities in a more effective manner because their inputs help to come up with decision that drives school activities sustainably	396	3.32	0.69	Often
5	gives the principal time to examine everything in depth before replying	396	2.37	0.59	Rarely
6	enables principals to communicate with the PTA for their inputs on vital issues of the school before taking decision	396	3.12	0.60	Often
7	allows me unlimited time to receive messages from all stakeholders thereby enabling enriched decision making	396	3.69	0.57	Always
8	affords principals opportunity to send direct messages to stakeholders about the progress of the school	396	3.36	0.93	Often

Result in table 1 showed that principals always use social media on items 1, 2, and 7, often use them on items 3, 4, 6 and 8, but rarely use them to enhance school-community collaboration in secondary schools in Ebonyi State as indicated on item 5.

Research Question 2: *To what extent do principals' use Social Media to encourage teamwork among staff in secondary school administration in Ebonyi State?*

In table2 below, data gotten from respondents were analysed to show the extent principals use social media to encourage teamwork among staff in secondary schools in Ebonyi State.

Table 2: Mean responses of the respondents on the extent principals' use Social Media to encourage teamwork among staff in secondary schools in Ebonyi State

S/N	Items: Social Media	N	Mean	S.D.	Decision
9	affords principals opportunity to spend quality time with stakeholders	396	2.41	0.59	Rarely
10	affords the principal opportunity to engage with other principals on administrative discourse which enriches their decision making in vital school matters	396	3.24	0.64	Often
11	Principals communicate issues of the school easily to staff/parents through social media even when it involves a complex decision	396	3.29	0.58	Often
12	helps principals to engage and manage staff activities in a more effective manner because staff inputs help principals come up with decision that drives school activities sustainably	396	2.36	0.93	Often
13	affords principals time to engage with stakeholders on issues affecting the school thoroughly before taking actions	396	2.81	0.89	Often
14	enables principals to communicate with the PTA for their inputs on vital issues of the school before taking decisions	396	3.13	0.78	Often
15	allows principals unlimited time to receive messages from all stakeholders thereby enabling enriched decision making	396	3.05	0.66	Often

Result in table2 showed that principals often use social media on items 10, 11, 12, 13,14, and 15, but rarely use them to encourage teamwork among staff in secondary schools in Ebonyi State as indicated on item 9.

DISCUSSIONS

From the outcome of analysis, it was shown that principals in public secondary schools in Ebonyi State always use social media to spend time in order to properly compose text messages so as to get the best inputs from stakeholders, affords the them opportunity to engage with other principals on administrative discourse which enriches their decision making in vital school matters, and allows them unlimited time to receive messages from all stakeholders thereby enabling enriched decision making. More so, principals often use social media to communicate issues of the school easily to staff/parents even when it involves a complex decision, manage the staff activities in a more effective manner because their inputs help to come up with decision that drives school activities sustainably, communicate with the PTA for their inputs on vital issues of the school before taking decision, send direct messages to stakeholders about the progress of the school, but rarely gives the principal time to examine everything in depth before giving their reply. Furthermore, there was no significant difference in the mean responses of urban and rural principals regarding their use of social media tools to enhance school-community collaborations. The findings are in line with that of Wiyono, Komariah, Alghamdi, Sultoni and Fahleri (2023) assessed the effect of principals' e-leadership on the effectiveness of schools' public relations and school improvement and found that there is a direct influence of principals' e-leadership on the effectiveness of schools' public relations. A point corroborated in research by Cox and McLeod (2014) who qualitatively described, analyzed, and interpreted the experiences of school principals who use multiple social media tools with stakeholders as part of their comprehensive communications practices and found that social media tools allow for greater interactions between school principals and their stakeholders, provide stronger connections to local stakeholders, to fellow educators, and to the world. More so, the responses of the respondents revealed no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents based on their areas of operations on the benefits social media can bring to bear in maintain strong-positive school-community collaboration. A point validated in research by Wiyono et al. (2023) that location of

operation, has no consequence on respondents perspective regarding to the instrumentality of social media in fostering school-community relationship effectively. This implies that principals of public secondary schools in Ebonyi State, Nigeria can leverage on social media platforms to maintain healthy relationship with the host communities which has been proven to aid in ensuring that adequate instructional materials aid, are provided to the schools.

In line with this theme, it found that social media rarely affords public secondary school principals in Ebonyi State opportunity to spend quality time with stakeholders, but often affords them the opportunity to engage with other principals on administrative discourse which enriches their decision making in vital school matters, and communicate issues of the school easily to staff/parents through social media even when it involves a complex decision. In addition, social media often helps principals to engage and manage staff activities in a more effective manner because staff inputs help principals come up with decision that drives school activities sustainably, and affords principals time to engage with stakeholders on issues affecting the school thoroughly before taking actions. It was also found that social media often enables principals to communicate with the PTA for their inputs on vital issues of the school before taking decision, as well as allows principals unlimited time to receive messages from all stakeholders thereby enabling enriched decision making. More so, there was no significant different in the opinion of urban and rural principals on the use of social media to encourage teamwork among staff in secondary schools in Ebonyi State. This is corroborated in research by Olowo et al. (2020) and Tamir et al. (2020) who reported that school administrative from different regions did not differ significantly in their responses regarding the impact of social media in encouraging teamwork among staff. they further posit that staff find it a veritable tool through which they can relate with and share ideas with the administrator and other colleagues without necessarily meeting physically. This implies that public secondary school principals can leverage on social media tools to enhance teamwork among staff in ensuring effective secondary school administration in Ebonyi State.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that to enhance school-communication collaboration effectively and encourage robust teamwork among staff, public secondary school principals in Ebonyi State can be leveraged on social media platforms to enhance communication with staff and manage conflicts among staff.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In line with the findings of the study recommends that secondary school principals should embrace social media platforms to enhance school-community relationship and foster teamwork among staff effectively.

Authors Contribution

Mkpuma, Okoro: Developed the content of the study

Prof. U. Aja-Okrie: Ensured review of the study's content

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